

A Geospatial Technology Approach to Wind-Farm Site Selection in Akure South Local Government Area, Ondo State

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Abstract:

This study aims to assess the suitability of locations for wind turbine farms. The study employed a GIS-based approach coupled with AHP techniques to identify the most suitable locations for Wind Turbine Farm installations in Akure South Local Government Area (LGA) Nigeria. The dataset used were the extracted attributes of criteria for wind farm establishment adopted from those harvested from previous researches. These attributes were acquired from relevant sources most online and the Global Positioning System (GPS) instrument field work; and subjected to various appropriate geospatial and analytical hierarchical processing and analysis. The

resultant suitability map identified key area for probable wind energy farm establishment. The result showed that 15.058% (5150.52ha) of the study area situated mostly at the Northern and Central part of the study area, and very sparsely across other parts, are suitable for the establishment of wind turban farm, out of which 0.03% (8.46 ha) are very suitable. 67.47% (22316.85 ha) mostly around the central part and sparsely all over the study area are moderately suitable. Area of low suitability covered 16.95%, and located at the Southern and North-Western part of the study area. The research was recommended as a guidepost for green energy use, for provision of autonomy in electricity distribution, as a prompt for more research for the establishment of wind turbines farms to bridge the energy gap and ensure energy security for the commercial and industrial sectors in the area.

Keywords: *Distribution, Establishment, GIS and AHP techniques, Suitability, Wind Farm.*

Introduction

Developing countries face a significant challenge in adopting renewable energy sources. Nigeria, with a population of 1.404 billion people, has a crucial goal of producing clean and sustainable energy. Wind turbines have gained increasing interest in recent years as a renewable energy source. The primary function of wind turbines is to harness the power of wind and convert it into electricity. Such installations aim to maximize productivity while minimizing additional costs, as well as environmental and social impacts. An

important issue before planning the development and implementation of a wind turbine farm is to search for the most appropriate technologies and some potential sites for implementing them. We consider the issue of locating the most suitable areas for deploying offshore wind turbines as a geographical and multi-criteria decision problem. This approach aims to provide the maximum flexibility at the decision level to favor different scenarios and priorities. The maritime domain has its constraints due to a combination of anthropic and environmental issues (Douvere

2008). For the deployment of an offshore wind turbine farm, a series of human-based and natural constraints should be considered such as human activity (e.g., fishing areas, maritime navigation routes), and physical parameters (e.g., wind, water depth).

The world is shifting towards sustainable energy sources, and wind energy significantly contributes to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and combating climate change. (Chaurasiya, et al., 2023). This is indicated in research by Chaurasiya and Kuo, emphasizing the importance of reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Wind farms are installed rapidly, e.g., by 33% in the EU in 2022. More than 38,000 large offshore wind turbines will be installed across the globe by 2036, significantly adding to the world's renewable energy capacity. By the end of 2023, the industry will reach a historic milestone—1 terawatt of wind energy installed worldwide (NBC news, 2023). However, the question of where to place new wind farms has become a topic of intense scientific research and public discussion due to the increasing demand for clean energy (Azizi, et al., 2014; Resak, et al., 2022). As we work towards a sustainable energy future, it is crucial to identify suitable locations for wind farms. Factors such as wind resource potential (wind speed) (Baban, et al., 2001), land availability (land cover classification) (Nitsch, et al., 2019), impact on nature and humans (the aesthetic of the landscape, acoustic environment, shadow flickering, and wind turbines electromagnetic interference) (Katsaprakakis, 2012) social acceptance (survey with the use of the questionnaire and the analysis of the content of strategic documents of the voivodeships) (Witkowska-Dabrowska, et al., 2021) and grid integration (distance to the power grid and roads) (Szurek et al., 2014 & Sliz- Szkliniarz, and Vogt. 2011) all play an essential role in the successful development and operation of wind power projects.

Wind turbines are used to generate electricity for individual homes or buildings, or for a group of houses or buildings. A wind farm is a collection of these turbines in a specific location, used together to produce electricity. The rotor blades of a wind turbine work like an airplane wing or

helicopter rotor blade, turning wind energy into electricity using aerodynamic force. When wind flows across the blade, the air pressure on one side of the blade decreases, creating both lift and drag. The force of the lift is stronger than the drag, causing the rotor to spin. The rotor is connected to the generator, either directly (if it's a direct drive turbine) or through a gearbox that speeds up the rotation and allows for a physically smaller generator. This process of converting aerodynamic force to rotation of a generator produces electricity.

Wind flow patterns and speeds vary greatly across the United States and are influenced by factors such as bodies of water, vegetation, and differences in terrain. Humans harness this wind flow, also known as motion energy, for various purposes such as sailing, flying kites, and generating electricity.

The increasing demand for renewable energy sources, especially in developing countries such as Nigeria, justifies this project. Wind energy is a sustainable and clean alternative that can help meet the growing electricity demand. Despite the rise in energy access, efficiency, and renewable energy sources in many developing nations, almost half of Nigerians (43.5%) still lack access to electricity, as reported by Momoh et al. (2018). Nigeria is also among the countries with the largest electricity access gap. Developing various sectors of the national economy, such as communication and industry, can improve access to safe drinking water, better healthcare facilities, and power. Therefore, exploring alternative energy sources like wind can enhance and supplement the nation's power generation capacity. Identifying suitable locations for wind turbines is crucial, given the rapid installation of wind farms worldwide, including offshore installations. This project focuses on optimal site selection in Akure, laying the foundation for broader efforts to establish renewable energy infrastructure. It could pave the way for future sustainable energy initiatives in Akure and Nigeria

The Study Area

Akure South Local Government Area (Figure 1) lies within Latitude 7° 05' 11" N to 7° 20' 53" N

and longitude 5° 04' 52" E to 5° 22' 00" E. Akure South Local Government Area is rich in natural and cultural resources that have the potential to promote the growth of tourism. A variety of

ethnic groups populate the area, each adding to the region's cultural diversity. The region is a fast-growing city with a good road network.

STUDY AREA MAP OF AKURE SOUTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, AKURE, ONDO STATE.

Figure 1. The Study Area-Nigeria/Ondo State/Akure South L.G.A

Material and Methods

Several factors were taken into consideration to choose the best location in the study area for the siting of a wind turbine farm. This was approached by harvesting several criteria for the siting of a wind turbine farm from previous researches. These includes wind resource, slope, and accessibility by road, proximity to the electricity network, and distance from airports, wind speed, elevation, slope, highways and railways, built-up areas, forest zones, and scenic areas (example, Flora, *et al.*, (2021) and Bennui *et al.*,(2007)). Eight criteria modified from the

harvested were adopted in determining the compatibility of the study area to wind turbine farm. They are wind pattern, slope, land cover, aspect, distance from power lines, and distance from cities, distance from highways, and distance from rivers. These criteria were grouped for ease of analysis according to Charabi and Gastli, (2011) into three classes which are *economic* (distance from power lines, distance from roads, and distance from the river, distance to airports/sea ports); *environmental* (elevation, aspect, and slope); and *meteorological* (wind speed) factors

Appropriate datasets were acquired from which the adopted criteria can be analyzed as follows: The *wind speed data* of spatial resolution of 280m was downloaded as a raster (TIF image) from Global Wind Atlas site (<https://globalwindatlas.info>). The *Open Street Map (OSM)* data was downloaded from the open geographic database (<https://www.openstreetmap.org>) using the overpass api of a bounding box that covers the whole of the study area. This was first imported into QGIS 3.6 software environment to access and checked to validate its usefulness for analysis, and to understand the data and the available fields. The *roads and rivers data* were then extracted as shape-files from it through map query and imported into the ArcGIS 10.4 software environment for analysis. The *Digital Elevation model (DEM)*, a Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) data with spatial resolution of 30 meters, that was void-filled, was sourced from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Explorer (www.usgs.gov) platform. The *land cover data* was derived from the land use land cover classification of Sentinel 2 satellite imagery with a spatial resolution of 10m that was sourced from the ArcGIS living atlas (<https://livingatlas.arcgis.com>) platform. The *power line features data* was sourced as a zipped shape file from ENERGYDATA.INFO (<http://www.energydata.info>) platform.

The acquired DEM was clipped for the area of interest and this output was further used to create the slope, aspect and elevation map. The projected coordinate system WGS 1984 UTM Zone 32N was used for the geospatial processing as it measures distance in meters to take care of the vector files like roads, rivers, urban areas and power lines. Some of the acquired datasets were resampled as necessary so as to ensure that a uniform cell size is used in the course of the analysis. The wind speed data was clipped for the area of interest and was resampled to maintain homogeneity with the other data. All the geospatial data were resampled to 30 meters resolution. The vector shape files of roads, rivers, urban areas and power lines were all processed using Euclidean distance to ascertain

the distances from roads, rivers, urban areas and power lines, respectively. This helped to factor the condition of the proximity of the suitable site of solar farm to the features. The elevation of the study area were obtained from SRTM DEM (1-arc second). Both the slope and elevation data were extracted for the study area, using the study area's boundary shapefile as output extent. The DEM was also used to produce an aspect raster showing the direction of degree rise of elevation. All of the chosen criteria were categorized into bins between predetermined ranges with values 1, 2, 3, 4 & 5 being interpreted as very high, high, moderate, low, and very low, respectively. The criteria were reclassified into suitability bins (1-5) as appropriate.

The analytical hierarchy process (AHP), which translates the strength of each criterion according to expert opinion was used to determine the weights for all of the selected criteria. Questionnaires were created for this study, which was administered to five specialists in the field of wind energy. Microsoft Excel capability was used to develop the pairwise matrices and determine the final weights for each of the nine criteria. A multi-criteria decision method (MCDM) was used to examine many options in the context of several criteria and competing goals (Sánchez-Lozano *et al.*, 2013; Saaty, 1980). To ensure consistency in the comparisons and facilitate aggregation, the Pairwise Comparison matrix was normalized. The criteria weights were calculated and the weighted sum was obtained thus enabling the computation of the ratio so as to rank the criteria based on their respective ratios. The higher the ratio, the more consistent the judgments. The consistency index, CI that measures the inconsistencies of pairwise comparisons computed with equation 1 according to (Saaty, 1980) and Hamed (2017):

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \quad (1)$$

A measure of coherence of the pairwise comparisons was calculated in the form of

consistency ratio (CR) according to Hamed (2017) in Equation 2.

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \quad (2)$$

Where λ_{max} is the maximum eigen value of the matrix, n is the number of comparison, RI is the random consistency index, the average CI of the randomly generated comparisons .

The results of the AHP analysis were assessed to know the degree of inconsistency and decide whether the weights generated can be used for analysis according to Hamed (2017), Atanasova-Pacemka, T., Pachemka, Lapevski, M., Timovski, R (2014).

To produce the final suitability map, all criteria used were overlaid considering the weights. This was done using the raster calculator tool with the following map algebra expression: ("Windspeed" * 0.32) + ("Slope" * 0.27) + ("Elevation (m)" * 0.12) + ("Aspect" * 0.11) + ("LULC" * 0.08) + ("Power line distance (m)" * 0.04) + ("Road distance (m)" * 0.04) + ("Stream distance (m)" * 0.02)

Results and Discussion

The Criteria and AHP Weights

The eight criteria adopted to determine the suitable places for the location of wind farms in the study area and their weights obtained using the AHP MCDM were catalogued (Table 1).

Table 1. Adopted Criteria and Weights

Criteria	Wind speed	Slope	Elevation	Aspect	LULC	Power line (m)	Road (m)	Stream (m)
Code	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
Weights	0.32	0.27	0.12	0.11	0.08	0.04	0.04	0.02

Figure 2. Wind Farm Suitability Map for Akure South LGA, Nigeria

The Suitability Map

A composite map containing the weighted overlay of all the criteria resulted in the suitability

map of the study area (Figure 2). This map shows the places in the study area in their various

degrees of suitability for the locations of wind farms.

The suitability map reveals that the suitable places (Very high and high in green colour) are

majorly around the Northern and Central part of the study area and sparsely all over. The table 2 shows the distribution of the suitability scores across the study area.

Table 2. Suitability Distribution across the Study Area

Suitability	Percent coverage
Very High	0.03%
High	15.55%
Moderate	67.47%
Low	16.95%
Very Low	0.00%

From table 2 and figure 2, it was observed that 15.06% (5150.52ha) of the study area situated mostly at the Northern and Central part of the study area, and very sparsely across other parts, are suitable for the establishment of wind turban farm (that is, no much modification to be made on the criteria) out of which 0.03% (8.46 ha), meeting the conditions of the criteria, are very suitable. 67.47% (22316.85 ha) located mostly around the central part and sparsely all over the study area are observed to be moderately suitable. That is, if some of the criteria are worked upon and some *give and takes* are done on the sites, the wind farm can be established thereon. These criteria are site specific according to Arafat *et al.*, (2010); Azizi *et al.*, (2014); Al-Shabeeb *et al.*, (2016). Area of low suitability were observed to cover 16.95%, and located at the Southern and North-Western part of the study area, which means they should neither be considered for the establishment of the wind farm at all or a high but risky modifications be done on the criteria if the area remain the only option and siting becomes very inevitable.

Conclusion

The assessment of suitable locations for wind farm as an alternative source of electricity especially for the study area has become a global quest and a major paradigm shift in this modern era (Samuel Knight Energy, 2023; NBC news,

2023). The use of geospatial technology to aid this assessment has become a veritable tool in the science and technology, and the commercial world. The information obtained has brought to light the suitability or otherwise of the study area for the establishment of the up-coming alternative to power generation in a very nearing future especially in the developing countries like where the study area is domiciled. This is in line with 7th goal of the 2030 agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015 for “Affordable and Clean Energy: Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all” (National Geographic Education (2024).

Limitations to the Study

This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by presenting a comprehensive and systematic approach to wind farm site selection using GIS and AHP techniques. It emphasizes the importance of considering multiple criteria, including meteorological, environmental, and economic factors, in the decision-making process. However, it is essential to note that the findings of this study are based on the available data and expert opinions used in the AHP. As with any modelling exercise, uncertainties and limitations exists, and site-specific considerations should be taken into account for practical implementation. Further validation and

refinement of the model could be achieved through ground-truthing and incorporating additional data sources.

Recommendations

The research is an essential component of the sustainable development goals as it is recommended as a guidepost for green energy use. The results of this research is recommended to provide the state and its bordering states with autonomy in electricity distribution. The findings of the research thus prompts a proposal for more research for the establishment of wind turbines farms to bridge the energy gap and ensure energy security for the commercial and industrial sectors in the area.

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